

GOSC Annual Report 2022

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GOSC Annual Report 2022

Foreword

Prof. Jianhui Li
CODATA Vice President
CAS GOSC Project PI

Dear colleagues and friends,

We are delighted to present this GOSC Annual Report 2022. Preparing this publication has given us a valuable opportunity to reflect on our past and, most importantly, to share our progress with all stakeholders worldwide.

Looking back, the idea to co-design and co-build a global open science cloud originated at the CODATA 2019 Beijing Conference. Thanks to the seed funding from CAS and the strong support of CODATA, ISC as well as other strategic partners around the world, the concept outlined in a draft has now blossomed into an influential global initiative with a clearly articulated vision to enable innovative scientific discovery in the dynamically evolving global open science environment.

At the heart of this vision lies the belief that collaboration is the key to success. Over the past four years, GOSC has established a broad collaboration network spanning Europe, Africa, Latin America, Asia, Australia, and the Americas, and built a robust think tank within the community, comprising over 200 experts from around 40 countries and regions. With a great vision and a broad international network, we have a springboard from which to scale up the GOSC's activities and continue to increase its global impact in an open, transparent, and sustainable way.

Overall, 2022 was a busy but fruitful year for GOSC. In line with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science and other similar calls, we actively participated in various knowledge-sharing activities and contributed to the capacity-building of open science to achieve SDGs. To facilitate science communication and promote trustworthy scientific partnerships, we established the GOSC IPO in October, with joint support from CODATA and CNIC, CAS. It's also worth mentioning the GOSC testbed prototype system is under construction to integrate and display the research outcomes generated by GOSC Working Groups and Case Studies. In the long run, it will serve as a unified platform for GOSC members to share resources, initiate experiments, and seek collaborations across multiple disciplines under harmonized policies, interoperable protocols, transparent services, and sustained mechanisms.

Indeed, none of these achievements would have been possible without the efforts of everyone involved. Therefore, I would like to express my sincere gratitude for the dedication and support of all GOSC members. Looking ahead, we are confident that GOSC will accomplish even more in advancing the alignment and collaboration of global open science clouds toward the SDGs for our mutual benefit. Let's embark on the exciting journey ahead in the new year!

Dear colleagues and friends,

It gives me great pleasure to introduce this report to the international Open Science and FAIR data community.

Open Science brings together a number of important themes: it has roots in the longstanding principles of scientific transparency and reproducibility; it is concerned with ensuring global equity both in access to knowledge and participation in knowledge creation; and it seeks to harness the technologies of the digital age, including machine learning and AI, to maximise the effectiveness and impact of science. In this context, the FAIR principles offer an important guide for how we can maximise utility of data and metadata for use by humans and by machines. The UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science calls on member states to promote and enable international and inter-regional collaborations 'to optimize infrastructure use and joint strategies for shared, multinational, regional and national open science platforms, including through the promotion of research collaborations, sharing of open science infrastructures, technical assistance, transfer and coproduction of technology related to open science and exchange of good practices under mutually agreed terms'. The GOSC initiative seeks to respond directly to this call and we aim to provide a mechanism for the exchange of knowledge and expertise among the numerous initiatives that have emerged in recent years. Our mission in GOSC is to encourage cooperation, alignment, and ultimately interoperability, among existing and emerging Open Science Clouds (or Open Research Commons).

The report that follows demonstrates encouraging progress! As part of our Decadal Programme for the International Science Council, CODATA is honoured to play a coordinating role in this initiative. A methodology has been developed that addresses thematic challenges common to Open Science Clouds (governance, policy, technical infrastructure and interoperability) while anchoring this work in reference to concrete Case Studies. Many esteemed colleagues from around the world have contributed their efforts and expertise to the GOSC vision. CODATA is grateful to all these colleagues and for the excellent collaboration with CNIC, CAS: the creation of the GOSC International Programme Office is an important step and has enormously assisted with the momentum and coordination of activities.

Much remains still to be done! Most of all we invite greater collaboration and participation from the various Open Science initiatives around the world. This report provides an insight into what can be achieved and confirms the effectiveness of the approach. Imagine the progress we could make with a network of Programme Offices to resource and support the activities? I commend to you this report and cordially invite your collaboration with the GOSC initiative.

Dr. Simon Hodson
CODATA
Executive Director

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01 WHAT WE DO?

GOSC 2022: Key Highlights

Below we highlight some of the key developments and achievements within GOSC during the year 2022.

02 HOW WE CONNECT?

GOSC 2022: Progress

GOSC 2022: Progress

Capacity Building for Accessible and Inclusive Science

As stated in the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, Open Science has significantly transformed the way of knowledge production and distribution, thereby increasingly being recognised as a key accelerator for the achievement of the SDGs and a game-changer in bridging the science, technology, and innovation gaps and fulfilling the human rights to science. In light of this, CBAS cooperated with the CAS-TWAS SDIM, CODATA (and in particular its GOSC Initiative), CNIC-CAS, and other supporting agencies to launch the 2022 International Training Workshop on Open Science and SDGs (8.29-9.9).

This workshop covers several training topics, such as Open Science Policies, SDGs Data Resources, SDG Technologies, SDG Platforms, and Demonstrations. By providing a scientific and practical guide to the use of Big Earth Data, the objective of this event is to support GOSC capacity building on emerging open science technologies for SDGs research and actions. A total of 104 trainees from 35 countries and regions have been selected and recommended to join this event, with diverse backgrounds in science and industry. In the long run, this event will be a regular GOSC training activity to promote accessible and inclusive science for all.

Please accept sincere thanks on behalf of me and my country for organising and hosting these very important workshops. I cannot thank you enough for proving us with restless online support, sharing important documents, uploading video zoom records, frequent email contacts as well as responding to emails.

Your center is excellent at presenting and providing hands-on training and your organizational staff is one of the best in the world. Your efforts have substantially contributed to the quality of our interactions and your professionalism has overawed me. Being a part of the training workshops helps me to get knowledge and information. I look forward to a continued relationship with you in the future as well as create to a network with the same hood participant experts.

Xueting, your arrangements were perfect. I found everything to my satisfaction. You took care of our individual needs and made sure everyone was well taken care of. Thank you for managing the schedule of each day and making it a relaxing escape. I congratulate you for demonstrating the highest professional courtesies.

The success of the event, in no small part, goes to your professional staff. Your event coordination, crowd management and logistical support have made such a big event successful. Thank you for your gracious and kind hospitality and for sponsoring me.

Thank You So Much
Goitom Kelem

2022 International Training Workshop on Open Science and SDGs

Aug. 29 - Sep. 09 Online

GOSC 2022: Progress

Knowledge Sharing to Bridge the Academic and Scientific Gaps

Knowledge sharing is essential for GOSC to narrow the existing academic and scientific gaps between different countries and regions worldwide. In 2022, GOSC has been actively engaged in global science communication by hosting a number of 'internal' meetings and co-organising international webinars, workshops, and conferences.

GOSC Data IO WG conducted a series of knowledge-sharing webinars during the year 2022, including the discussions regarding Emerging Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (March 2022), Data IO WG Briefing on Case Studies (May 2022), Data Interoperability in Europe (July 2022), Data Interoperability in China (October 2022), and Data Interoperability in Australia (November 2022).

GOSC Data IO Workshop

In November, GOSC Biodiversity CS supported a Webinar on Exploring Camera-trap Data. The event described new FAIR data-sharing software, Camtrap DP, and the new data model that underpins it. The attendees also heard from leaders of several camera trap projects who outlined views on how the model and best practices documentation will enable data sharing from the different camera trap systems into our global infrastructure.

GOSC Biodiversity Webinar

GOSC first and second AHMs were held in June and October, respectively, to review the current progress of the GOSC initiative and to facilitate the engagement between various stakeholders.

GOSC AHM

At the 2022 IDW conference in June, GOSC TI WG, PL WG, and Data IO WG along with selected CSs such as SDG-13 and Radar Data conducted three breakout sessions to exchange experiences towards federated OSCs from political, technical, and data interoperable perspectives. The thematic sessions include Towards Federated Open Science Clouds: Technics and Demonstrations, Progress on Policy & Practice in OSCs: Key Issues and Disciplinary Showcases, and GOSC Data IO: Landscape Study and Case Studies in Data Interoperability.

IDW GOSC session

Jointly supported by EGI, CNIC, and ISC CODATA, the 3rd Global Open Science Cloud Workshop has been held in Prague and online on September 22nd, 2022, bringing together worldwide experts from international organizations, academic institutions, and businesses.

GOSC Workshop

In October 2022, the GOSC IPO launch event was held successfully online, with global stakeholders joining the discussion to share knowledge of worldwide open science practices and OSCs.

GOSC IPO Launch Event

GOSC 2022: Progress

GOSC International Governance Structure and Policy Research

GOSC has established an international governance structure to support the implementation and demonstration of the initiative, consisting of one SG, four WGs, five CSs, a Secretariat, and an IPO. A regular communication mechanism has been set up, including monthly SG calls, monthly Secretariat/IPO discussions, and regular working meetings of each WG and CS to foster internal coordination and cooperation within the GOSC community. In 2022, GOSC governance and policy research focused on a lightweight policy review focused on rules of participation of global OSCs/platforms (completed). Besides, other ongoing discussions include the exploration of a measurement tool entitled "Data Characteristics Affecting Levels of Openness", and guidelines for applying the UN Open Science Recommendation in GOSC.

GOSC Technical Validation: AAI Federation

GOSC aims to enable technical interoperation between and among digital research infrastructures worldwide in order to support the needs of science internationally, both individual scientists and collaborations of scientists from around the world. In 2022, GOSC TI WG was dedicated to promoting scalable and interoperable AAI collaboration across e-infrastructures and scientific communities. In order to understand the AAI development landscape from different countries/regions, a technical discussion workshop on AAI for GOSC was organised in March. AAI experts from Europe and China were invited to introduce their development and discuss the potential federated access or shared AAI solution.

“ In 2022, GOSC TI WG was dedicated to promoting scalable and interoperable AAI collaboration across e-infrastructures and scientific communities. ”

Description: Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure enabling secure access to e-infrastructures. A fully connected Global Open Science Cloud would need **scalable and interoperable AAI across e-infrastructures and scientific communities**. In order to understand the AAI development landscape from different countries/regions, we organise this workshop and invite AAI experts from Europe and China to introduce their development, and to discuss the integration solution.

Speakers

Dr Nicolas Liampotis is an AAI Research Engineer, at GRNET - Greek Research and Technology Network. He has participated in numerous national (funded by various public organisations, as well as private companies) and international (EU-funded) research and development projects (Tequila, Daidalos II, PERSIST, SOCIETIES, ECONET, VI-SEEM, EGI-Engage, EUDAT2020, MAGIC, AENEAS, AARC2, SeaDataCloud, EOSC-hub, N4OS-Europe). His role in these projects was that of an architecture designer, technical contributor, and software engineer, focusing on the design, development, evaluation, and optimization of solutions for trust management, privacy protection and federated access in distributed infrastructures. He is currently working at GRNET as a Trust & Identity engineer and is leading the development of the EGI Check-in Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure service that enables access to research data and services provided across the infrastructures participating in EOSC-hub. He is also involved in the architecture working group within the AARC Engagement Group for Infrastructures (AEGIS), which brings together representatives from research and e-infrastructures, operators of AAI services for a more effective uptake of AAI recommendations in their federated access solutions.

Prof. Jianhui Li is the director of Science and Technology Cloud Department at the Computer Network Information Center (CNIC) of the Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), and a Professor at the University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS). He obtained PhD on computer science from the Institute of Computing Technology of CAS in 2007. In 2016, He founded "China Scientific data", which is the first open access data journal for scientific data publication in China. Currently, he is leading the design, development and operation of CSTCloud (China Science and Technology Cloud), which is the national level open science platform. He also serves as the CODATA vice president.

Agenda

- 30' AAI Model and Standard in Europe, Presentation + Q&A, Nicolas Liampotis, GRNET, Europe
- 30' AAI Model and Standard in China, Presentation + Q&A, Jianhui Li, CNIC, China
- 60' Technical discussion

AARC Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration

AARC Architecture & Guidelines
AAI Model and Standard in Europe

Nicolas Liampotis (GRNET), et al. for the AARC Community

Technical Discussion workshop on AAI for GOSC
31 Mar, 2022

AAI Model and Standard in CSTCloud

LI Jianhui
Computer Network Information Center, CAS
@Technical Discussion on AAI model for GOSC framework 31st March 2022

The Beta Version of a GOSC Testbed Prototype

Jointly endorsed by the TI WG and CNIC technical team, a GOSC testbed prototype is under development. Following the open-science principles, this prototype assumes the responsibility to provide a robust technical validation for the further implementation of the GOSC initiative. The design of the generic technical framework was completed by the end of 2022. This prototype will enable federal aggregation at the IaaS, PaaS, and other levels, providing network interconnection, service interoperation, and community connectivity to its users and service providers. As a tangible system for open resources, technologies, communities, research, and governance, the prototype will support enhanced international research alignment within and outside the GOSC global network. As a joint effort of the GOSC community, its design and development will be further refined based on the feedback from the SG and other members to enhance the engagement among WGs and CSs.

“As a tangible system for open resources, technologies, communities, research, and governance, the prototype will support enhanced international research alignment within and outside the GOSC global network.”

Global Open Science Cloud

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Global Open Science Cloud

The mission of GOSC is to interconnect different institutional, national and regional open science clouds and platforms to create a global virtual environment for globalized research and innovation.

Learn more

GOSC WGs & CSs

“GOSC will encourage cooperation, alignment, and ultimately interoperability, between existing and emerging OSCs. As mentioned, we aim to do this through a combination of thematic WGs and a set of detailed CSs that will demonstrate how international collaborative research communities and projects can be supported by OSCs.”

For more introduction to each GOSC WG and CS, please turn to GOSC Flyer. Follow our progress and join us at: <https://bit.ly/GOSC-Sign-Up>

STRATEGY
GOVERNANCE
SUSTAINABILITY

TECHNICAL
INFRASTRUCTURE

FOUR INITIAL WG TOPICS
INCLUDE

POLICY AND LEGAL

DATA INTEROPERABILITY

SIX INITIAL LCS TOPICS INCLUDE

INCOHERENT
SCATTER
RADAR DATA
FUSION AND
COMPUTATION

SDG-13
CLIMATE
CHANGE AND
NATURAL
DISASTERS

OPEN
REPRODUCIBLE
RAW DIFFRACTION
DATA FOR ACCESS
IN PANDEMICS

INTEGRATING
MACHINE-DERIVED
CAMERA-TRAP DATA
INTO THE GLOBAL
SHARED SCIENCE
NETWORKS

SENSITIVE DATA
FEDERATION
ANALYSIS MODEL
IN POPULATION
HEALTH

FROM RAW
BIODIVERSITY
DATA TO
OPERATIONAL
INDICATORS
THROUGH THE
ESSENTIAL
BIODIVERSITY
VARIABLES (EBV-
OSC)

03 WHERE WE GO?

GOSC Work Plan 2023

Looking forward to 2023, GOSC will further engage with members and all global stakeholders, with a particular focus on the global south countries to ensure that no one is left behind in the development of global OSCs. In the new year, the working priority of the GOSC IPO will focus on capacity building and knowledge sharing. Strategic partnerships between the IPO with local and international organizations such as CENI, NSMC, and IRDR will be further implemented.

The GOSC Position Paper (White Paper) will be one of our key research outputs in the upcoming year. This roadmap is intended to clarify our motivation for uniting global OSCs, our vision, mission, and GOSC's significant progress of each WG and CS to global stakeholders. In addition, the 2022 annual report, as well as the first edition of the GOSC flyer, will be openly publicized as promotional materials to enhance the visibility of GOSC in the academic and scientific realms. During the AHM, GOSC key members have reached an agreement that the future plan within the GOSC community highlights several upcoming activities, including the regional SDG-13 service demonstration based on convergent research resources, thematic biodiversity webinar on innovative data models, interoperability analysis between radar data systems, scope review of the national health data ecosystems and FAIR implementation, data interoperability analysis based on a survey, as well as the potential joint collaboration between the Governance and Policy WG.

A series of international conferences and training workshops are being planned for 2023. Among them, the 2023 International Training Workshop (Beijing, 28 Aug–8 Sept) and the First International Symposium on Open Science Clouds (Beijing, 4–6 Sept) would be the branded events for GOSC to promote capacity building and knowledge sharing in the long run. In addition, IPO will represent GOSC internally to facilitate the organization of the GOSC All Hands Meeting (Online, TBC) and the 4th Global Open Science Cloud Workshop co-organized by the EGI, CODATA, and CNIC, CAS. Externally, GOSC will continue to engage in the 2023 SciDataCon/International Data Week (Salzburg, 23–26 October). As part of this feast of experience exchanges, the PL WG, Governance WG, and TI WG, along with several CS are planning to hold thematic sessions to communicate with global stakeholders and further expand the global influence of the GOSC initiative.

This annual report records some exciting and fruitful achievements within the GOSC community in the year 2022. With pride, we are advancing closer to our mission of encouraging cooperation, alignment, and ultimately interoperability among the various OSCs worldwide. In the upcoming new year, GOSC will continue to be committed to achieving its mission and vision. Welcome on board, and take pleasure in this fantastic journey with us!

04 LIST OF ACRONYMS

- 1 **AAI: Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure**
- 2 **AHM: All Hands Meeting**
- 3 **CAS-TWAS (SDIM): Chinese Academy of Sciences - The World Academy of Sciences (Centre of Excellence on Space Technology for Disaster Mitigation)**
- 4 **CBAS: International Research Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals**
- 5 **CENI: China Environment for Network Innovations**
- 6 **CNIC, CAS: Computer Network Information Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences**
- 7 **CODATA, ISC: Committee on Data of the International Science Council**
- 8 **CS: Case Study**
- 9 **Data IO WG: Data Interoperability Working Group**
- 10 **EGI: European Grid Infrastructure**
- 11 **FAIR: Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability**
- 12 **GOSC: Global Open Science Cloud**

- 13 **IDW: International Data Week**
- 14 **IPO: International Programme Office**
- 15 **IRDR: Integrated Research on Disaster Risk**
- 16 **ISC CODATA: Committee on Data of the International Science Council**
- 17 **MoU: Memorandum of Understanding**
- 18 **NSMC: National Satellite Meteorological Centre**
- 19 **OSC: Open Science Cloud**
- 20 **PL WG: Policy and Legal Working Group**
- 21 **SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals**
- 22 **SG: Steering Group**
- 23 **TI WG: Technical Infrastructure Working Group**
- 24 **WG: Working Group**

05 CONTACTS

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